

Compensation Under Land Acquisition Law – Concept, Parameters, Interpretation

Madhubala Sheokumar Shukla
(Research Scholar)
Email – madhubala1529@gmail.com

DR. HAIDER ALI
Head Legal Department
(Research Guide)
Institute of Legal Studies and Research
Mangalayatan University
33rd Milestone, Aligarh-Mathura Highway,
Beswan, Aligarh -202146 (U.P) India.

Abstract:

Compensation is embedded in Eminent Domain which means supreme power of the Govt. to acquire the property of any person without his consent in the interest of the General Public, however subject to payment of compensation. During Constituent Assembly Debates the question of public purpose, the Govt. authorised with the power of eminent domain, and the compensation were intricately linked mainly because of the issue of zamindari. Battle between the Parliament and the Supreme Court ensued over expropriation and compensation and through a series of amendments to the Constitution it ultimately culminated into removal of “Right to Property” from fundamental right under 44th Amendment (which deleted Art. 19(1)(f) and Article 31 and inserted in Part XII a new Chapter IV right to property under Article 300A) and made it a legal right, hence eminent domain is now a matter of Statute Law. (Public purpose and compensation are omitted from Art. 300A). However payment of compensation is a constitutional requirement under Article 30(1A) and 2nd Proviso to Art. 31A(1). The Hon’ble Supreme Court in **K T Plantation Pvt. Ltd. And another Vs. State of Karnatka** on 9th August 2011 has observed that “118. *Payment of compensation now depends on terms of the Statute and Legislative Policy....143(e) Public purpose is a precondition for depriving a person of his property under Art. 300A and right to claim compensation is also inbuilt in that Article ... (f) Statute depriving a person of his property is therefore amenable to judicial review...*” Highly valuable fundamental rights under the Constitution of India are Articles 21, 14, 19 and are considered as holy trinity consisting of a ‘golden triangle’. Power of Eminent Domain emerged and developed in India under East India Company Rule. Right from 1824 Act till 1894 Land Acquisition Act and its amendments from time to time at pre-independence stage, there is change in the Parameters of determination of compensation and Authorities who could adjudicate the same. Viz. in 19th Century the amount was to be determined by the Arbitrators. In 1870 Act system of proper valuation of land was incorporated. If a person was not agreeable to the amount offered to him, then Collector could make a reference to Civil Court assisted by Assessors. Further the Appeal could be filed to High Court. Bill of 1893 contained a definition for market value, however it was dropped by Select Committee. In the Act of 1894, market value was not defined. It has been amended in British Era in 1914, 1919, 1920, 1921, 1923, 1933, 1938, 1945. Also arose the theory of “value to the Owner” i.e. value which a Willing Seller may expect from a Willing Purchaser in the open market. (**Raja Vyricherla Narayana Gajapatraju Badadur Garu v. The Revenue**

Received: 22 February 2024

Revised: 2 March 2024

Final Accepted 12 March 2024

29

Divisional Officer, Vizagapatam, ILR 1939 Mad 532 (known as the Chemudu case). Post independence 1894 Act went through various amendments in 1962,1967 however major amendments took place in 1984 . The Amendments tend towards providing limitation period for various stages of acquisition process and adding the elements of compensation viz. interest was raised from 6% to 9% on the Court awarding excess compensation, if the Collector invokes urgency power, before taking possession, 80% of compensation be paid [Section 17(3A)]. Recently the Hon'ble Bombay HC has held Section 17 proceedings have lapsed citing a Judgment of Hon'ble SC in M/s Delhi Airtech Services Pvt. Ltd. And Anr. , “ *if the prerequisite condition for payment of 80% before taking possession is not complied...by legal fiction it loses its character as acquisition under Section 17 [and (acquisition)] ...will lapse.*” Chapter VII laid down provisions for acquisition of land by Companies, 15% sum was raised to 30% on market value. The said Act was replaced by 2013 Act which combines compensation with rehabilitation and resettlement and provision of infrastructural Amenities in resettled area, enhanced compensation , interest and solatium (100%) etc . However Maharashtra State Acts relating to land acquisition exempted from applicability of RFCT LARR Act 2013 (Section 105A, Schedule V of the Maharashtra Amendment Act 2018). Certain provisions relating to determination of Compensation and rehabilitation and resettlement under Schedule I, II and III of RFCT LARR Act got incorporated in Maharashtra State Acts by way of Amendments . This has resulted in limited applicability and dilution of 2013 Act. I have studied the various case Laws of Supreme Court and Bombay High Court relating to interplay of acquisition and compensation provisions under various Central and State Laws relating to Land Acquisition vis a vis 2013 Act , which gives a Kaleidoscope of varied pleas and principles in judgments viz. Doctrine of Reference , Doctrine of incorporation which points towards limited applicability of 2013 Act to Maharashtra State Acts , There are conflicting judgments , Hon'ble Courts granting interest in case of delay in compensation , inadequate compensation , plea of paucity of funds by acquiring body , many a times for doing complete justice , the Hon'ble Supreme Court has to invoke Art. 142 of the Constitution . Invariably the Award is challenged on the basis of inadequate compensation , non payment of compensation, interest for delay , rent for taking possession of land prior to institution of acquisition proceedings etc. The *In Dilbagh Rai Jarry v. Union of India, (1974) 3 SCC 554*, the Hon'ble Supreme Court, speaking through Justice Krishna Iyer, after reference to the National Policy on State litigation ... lamented that the State Government routinely disregards such policies and institute appeals, which result in staggering litigation costs and staggering litigation volumes.” (Also see judgment of Bombay High Court in **State of Maharashtra Versus Smt. Sharadabai Ganesh Oze ... Respondent**; Decided on 3 April 2017)ⁱ The conclusion points out the need for a uniform regime of compensation , clarity in Rules for determination of compensation for enhancing accuracy at the first rung in Hierarchy , balance between private and Public interests, a generous compensation regime for the persons interested will increase costs of the Govt. or acquiring body however at the same time it may mitigate defiance by persons affected, which will reduce litigation , delay and inflationary costs .

Keywords – eminent domain, compensation , interest ,solatium , rent , rehabilitation and resettlement , delay , inadequate , uniform , National litigation Policy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Compensation has its source in Eminent Domain which means supreme power of the Govt. to acquire the property of any person without his consent in the interest of the General Public , however subject to payment of compensation . In all modern constitutions of the World of democratic nature , payment of compensation is the condition to exercise the right of expropriation. Various Principles regarding acquisition and liability to pay compensation and that no appropriation can be made save by Authority of Law were summed up under Section 299 of the Govt. of India Act 1935. During Constituent Assembly Debates the question of public purpose , the Govt. authorised with the power of eminent domain, and the question of compensation were intricately linked mainly because of the issue of zamindari. Contradictory ideas were put forth in Objective Resolution. On the one hand , the Constituent Assembly members were influenced by the American constitution, the shielding given by the Bill of Rights and its enforcement by the independent judiciary. On the other hand, they were also influenced by the objects of a more equitable society, which were brought into effect mainly through Govt. intervention in the socialist and communist countries, where there were no rights in the private property, and all property was owned by the Govt. Various views were put forth viz. *“when the government pursued socially beneficial legislation, such as zamindari abolition, then that power must not be limited, , nor should there be a requirement to pay “just compensation” . , “ if the government were to acquire property for its own use (to build roads, etc), then its authority must be curtailed and require payment of compensation.”(Pant).ⁱⁱ* Art. 31 in its original version was drafted . Strong shield for the individual rights against compulsory acquisition only exempting Zamindari from its purview , was opined .

Highly valuable fundamental rights under the Constitution of India are Articles 21,14,19 and are considered as holy trinity consisting of a ‘golden triangle’. Draft constitution of India 1948 in Entry 9 State List (List II) provided ,” *Compulsory acquisition of land except for the purposes of Union subject to the provisions of List III with respect to regulations of principles on which compensation is to be determined for property acquired or requisitioned for the purposes of the State.*” Entry 35 in the Concurrent list in Seventh Schedule to Constitution provided - *“Principles on which compensation is to be determined for property acquired or requisitioned for the purposes of the Union or of a State”*. and the Union List Entry 43 provided for *“regulation of the principles on which compensation is to be determined for property acquired or requisitioned for the purposes of the Union .”* The word “compensation” appearing in draft Constitution 1948 was removed from the Entries under constitution/ 7th

Amendment under which single Entry in Concurrent list was substituted. Law Commission Report Relating To Land Acquisition (10th Report)(3rd May 1956) showed concern –“ *There is no uniformity either in the principles for determination of compensation or in the Tribunals constituted for determining it .*” **Also that , “ that there are unconscionable delays in the determination of compensation and its payment to the owners of properties... ”** Battle between the Parliament and the Supreme Court ensued through a series of Case Laws and amendments to Constitution over expropriation and compensation , Property rights , also through a series of amendments to the Constitution viz. In the **State Of West Bengal Vs. Mrs. Bela Banerjee And Others, 11 Dec. 1953** ⁱⁱⁱ The Hon’ble Supreme Court had said while interpreting Article 31(2) as then stood , “*Whether such principles take into account all the elements which make up the true value of the property appropriated and exclude matters which are to be neglected, is a justiciable issue to be adjudicated by the court.*” ^{iv} **The Constitution fourth amendment Act 1955 was enacted to overcome the effect of this decision i.e. justiciability of the adequacy of compensation was taken out of the purview of the Court viz “...no such law shall be called in question in any court on the ground that the compensation provided by that law is not adequate.”**

The Constitution (Seventeenth Amendment) Act, 1964 added a proviso to Article 31A by way of amendment that -

“... where any land ... is held by a person under his personal cultivation, it shall not be lawful for the State to acquire any portion of such land as is within the ceiling limit ... or any building or structure standing thereon or appurtenant thereto, unless the law relating to the acquisition of such land, building or structure, provides for payment of compensation at a rate which shall not be less than the market value thereof.”;

Twenty Fifth Amendment (1971) –This Amendment Act was passed to nullify the effect of the judgment of Hon’ble Supreme Court in **R. C. Cooper Vs. Union of India** - The word "compensation" was omitted from article 31(2) and replaced by the word "amount". The said amount may be given otherwise than in cash.

In Kesavananda Bharati Sripadagalvaru and Ors Vs State of Kerala and Anr ., dated 24/04/1973 .various issues came up. Supreme Court formulated the “Basic Structure Doctrine” and observed that “*The expression "amendment of this Constitution" does not enable Parliament to abrogate or take away, fundamental rights or to completely change the fundamental features of the Constitution so as to destroy its identity. Within these limits Parliament can amend every article.*”

The Constitution (Forty-Fourth Amendment) Act, 1978-The 44th Amendment deleted remaining part of the right to private property. Article 19(1)(f) and Article 31 were omitted and in CHAPTER IV RIGHT TO PROPERTY a single clause was put to the following effect -

“300A No person shall be deprived of his property save by authority of law.”.

In the objects it was mentioned that , *“the right of persons holding land for personal cultivation and within the ceiling limit to receive compensation at the market value would not be affected.”*

The History of Land Laws relating to acquisition shows that in 19th Century the amount was to be determined by the Arbitrators . In 1870 Act system of proper valuation of land was incorporated . If a person was not agreeable to the amount offered to him , then Collector could make a reference to Civil Court assisted by Assessors . If no agreement is reached , the Appeal could be filed to High Court . The 1894 Act as amended does not define compensation but defines the person interested as including all *persons “claiming an interest in compensation to be made on account of acquisition of land under this Act .”* Part II refers to Collector making the Award (under Section 11) regarding compensation and apportionment of compensation . Part III (Section 18 to 28) relate to proceedings before Reference Court where determination of compensation is based on criteria mentioned in Section 23 (matters to considered for determining the compensation) and Section 24 (matters to be neglected in determining the compensation.) . For acquisition of land for Companies (Part VII) previous consent of Govt. and Agreement with Govt. necessary which should interalia provide for payment to appropriate Govt. of the cost of acquisition. The said Act was repealed by Right to Fair Compensation and Transparency in Land Acquisition, Rehabilitation and Resettlement Act 2013 which provided for enhanced compensation (Section 26 to 30 read with 1st Schedule) and also for Rehabilitation and Resettlement and provision for Infrastructural Amenities (Section 31(1) , 32 , 38(1) and 105(3) read with Second and Third Schedule). However there is plethora of Central Laws and Maharashtra State Laws relating to acquisition of land prescribing different compensation as well as methods of determination of compensation which are not uniform and often result in discrimination . viz. There are 13 Central Acts mentioned in IVth Schedule of 2013 Central Act and 4 Acts mentioned in Vth Schedule of Maharashtra Amendment 2018 to 2013 Central Act to which provisions of 2013 Act are not applicable . The Courts have often interpreted the provisions of 2013 Act as having limited Applicability to State Acts for eg. In **Sahebrao Bhausaheb Kalate Versus State of Maharashtra and Others , Decided on August 7, 2019** , the Hon’ble Bombay High Court has held , *“section 24 is a special case of application of the Act (2013Act) in retrospective cases, ... with a view to ensure that the land owners/Farmers/affected Families get enhanced compensation under the provisions of RFCTLAR & R Act of 2013 ...the benefits accruable in reference to the acquisition proceedings initiated under the provisions of the Land Acquisition Act, (1894) cannot be automatically made applicable in cases of acquisition, governed under the MRTP Act.”*

As stated by P. Suresh Babu - *“In case of Maharashtra, it would thus be seen that, there are different procedures and different methods of determining the compensation amounts of*

acquisition in different Acts. It is, in all fairness to the public and landowners, necessary that, there is uniformity.” v

The present Article provides an insight into the concept , legal framework , principles , determination of compensation as progressed in India from British Era till date under Central and Maharashtra State laws relating to Land Acquisition and how these provisions were interpreted by the Courts, as Parameters changed from time to time . Eminent Domain power shall be so exercised that infrastructure development projects should not suffer, however at the same time a generous compensation regime for the persons interested be devised The Owner who is dispossessed from land shall have a right under law to adequate compensation and reasonable protection shall be devised for the exercise of such power . There should be uniformity, simplicity and transparency in the methods of determination of compensation at the initial rung itself which will satisfy the persons interested and curtail delay , reduce litigation and mitigate disgruntlement and defiance .

2. LEGAL FRAMEWORK ON COMPENSATION

2.1. British Era –

Regulation 1 of 1824 can be said to be first statutory Law on land acquisition in India , which mentions in its objects , *“a just and full compensation may be secured to all persons , holding an interest in the property so appropriated .”* Fair value meant the net rent from the land and the value of other interests therein . Under Act of 1850 compensation was settled by Agreement or if it could not be reached, by procedure under Regulation of 1824. Matter would be referred to Arbitrators four in number who would then appoint an Umpire . Opinion of majority would determine the Award . In case of dispute relating to apportionment of compensation, matter would be referred to Court . Act of 1857 was passed under which Arbitrators were reduced to two with the third to be appointed by them. Compensation included , besides value of land , damage which may be sustained by any person interested in respect of adjoining land (Section 26) . Act of 1861 provided for temporary occupation . In 1863 Act provision was made for acquisition of land for *“construction of works of public utility by private persons or Companies”*. Agreement was made by Private persons or Companies with the Govt. for payment of the price of the land for the proposed work. Right to mine or minerals lying under the land would not pass unless compensation for the same is expressly allowed in the Award. Act of 1857, 1863 and 1861 were repealed by Act of 1870 and a separate Act of 1885 for mines and minerals was passed . Under the Act of 1870 , instead of Arbitrators , the Collector , if no

agreement is reached with the persons interested , would refer the matter for determination to Court assisted by two assessors ; in case of disagreement with the Assessors , Judge’s view would prevail but was subject to Appeal to District Judge or High Court . Rules relating to principles of compensation were first laid down in Act of 1870.(Section 24 and 25) . Act of 1870 was replaced by Act of 1894 .Bill of 1893 contained a definition for market value , however it was deleted by Select Committee. In the Act of 1894 market value was not defined . It has been amended in British Era in 1914 , 1919,1920,1921, 1923,1933, 1938, 1945.

Amendment Act of 1921 - Section 54 of Land Acquisition Act was amended to include limited right of Appeal to Privy Council as mentioned therein.

Amending Act of 1923 - Material time for market value of land is date of Notification under Section 4(1) and not date of Declaration under Section 6.

Land Acquisition Bombay Amendment Act 1938 (applicable in Province of Bombay) – “In Section 28 and 34 of the Land Acquisition Act 1894 , for the word “six” the word “four “ shall be substituted .” (interest on excess compensation awarded by Court) .

Land Acquisition (Bombay Amendment) Act 1945 . In Land Acquisition Act 1894 -Part IA was inserted comprising of Section 3A which related to Preliminary Survey by the officers of Provincial Govt. by issuing prior 7 days Notice and shall at the time of entry make payment of necessary damage to be done as aforesaid.

Procedure for determination of compensation under Act of 1894 – Collector tries to settle the amount by Agreement . If there is no such Agreement , Collector makes his own Award . Party aggrieved can obtain a reference to Special Judge where an adjudication like that of a Civil Court will occur. In case of several persons claiming compensation matter will be referred by Collector to the Reference Judge to whom money will be transferred for disposal as per adjudication . Compensation provisions are mainly contained in Section 23 and 24 . As per Section 23(1) certain parameters are given for determination of compensation viz. Market value on the date of Notification under Section 4(1) , damage sustained for the reasons mentioned therein , person compelled to change his residence or place of business . As per Section 23(2) a sum of 15% on such market value in consideration of the compulsory nature of such acquisition would be awarded . Certain principles have been evolved viz. principle of “potential value “ including “Special adaptability” of land which enhances its value . Also arose the theory of “value to the Owner” i.e. value which a Willing Seller may expect from a Willing Purchaser in the open market. In **Land Acquisition Officer vs. Fakir Mahammad (1933)**

Received: 22 February 2024

Revised: 2 March 2024

Final Accepted 12 March 2024

35

.143, I.C. 699 method of valuation is given as , “ (1) price paid , within a reasonable time for the land (2) the rents and profits of the land received shortly before acquisition (3) prices paid for adjacent lands possessing similar advantages, and (4) opinions of valuers and experts .” vi

The Privy Council in **Raja Vyricherla Narayana Gajapatraju Badadur Garu v. The Revenue Divisional Officer, Vizagapatam, ILR 1939 Mad 532** (known as the Chemudu case)- “...The principles which regulate the fixing of compensation of lands compulsorily acquired ... substance ...that the value to be ascertained is the value to the seller of the property in its actual condition at the time of expropriation with all its existing advantages and with all its possibilities, excluding any advantage due to the carrying out of the scheme for which the property is compulsorily acquired, the question of what is the scheme being a question of fact for the arbitrator in each case....”

“24. It remains to deal with Section 24(5) of the Land Acquisition Act. That subsection as applied to the present case means no more than this : that in valuing the appellant's land on February 13, 1928, it must be valued as it then stood, and not as it would stand when the land had been acquired ...”vii

2.2. After Independence till repeal of 1894 Land Acquisition Act various amendment Acts to 1894 Act were enacted .

- **Supreme Court of India , in Smt. Somavanti And Others vs The State Of Punjab And Others(And ... on 2 May, 1962^{viii} has observed as follows – The contention was that** the property is in fact being acquired for a company and, therefore, the provisions of Part VII of the Act should have been complied with . **The alleged contribution of Rs. 100 made by the Government** is a colourable exercise of power, **The Hon’ble Court (Majority Judgment) observed that** “The question whether any of the aforesaid purposes falls within the expression public purpose would arise for consideration only if the declaration of the Government is not conclusive or if the action of the Government is colourable”

Minority Judgment -“The proviso (s.6(1) and proviso thereof) says that the compensation shall be paid by the company or, wholly or partly, out of public revenues.... The payment of a part of a compensation must have some rational relation to the compensation payable in respect of the acquisition for a public purpose. So construed "part" can only mean a substantial part of the estimated compensation. ...”

- **Amended by Act 13 of 1967- Limitation period for Section 6 Declaration was 2 years . Section 4(3) of the Act however provided interest *calculated at the rate of six per centum per annum on the market value of such land, as determined under Section 23 of the Act, if “declaration is or has been made after the expiry of three years from the date of publication of such notification”*. **Proviso to Section 4(3) - “Provided that no such interest shall be payable for any period during which the proceedings for the acquisition of any land were held up on account of stay or injunction by order of a court”****
- The Hon’ble Supreme Court of India in **Indrajit C. Parekh Of Ahmedabad ... vs State Of Gujarat And Ors. on 18 March, 1975** has observed as follows (Section 6(1) – (pre 1984)

“We would however guard ourselves against being understood to say that a token contribution by the State towards the cost of acquisition will be sufficient compliance with the law in each and every case. ...”
- **Land Acquisition (Amendment) Act, 1984-**

TABLE I

COMPENSATION PROVISIONS UNDER 1894 ACT (AS AMENDED IN 1984) -ix

Section	Particulars
17(3) (3A)	Emergency provision - Collector shall at the time of taking possession compensation for standing crops or trees and other damage due to sudden dispossession. Before taking possession shall tender 80% of the compensation
23 (1)	Determination of amount of compensation – Market value of land at the date of publication of Section 4 (1) Notification
	Damage sustained – *Due to taking of Standing crops trees on the land *By reason of severing of such land from his other land *Reasonable expenses if he is compelled to change his residence or place of business *Diminution of profits between the period from Section 6 Declaration to Collector’s taking possession of land
23(1A)	Interest @ twelve per centum per annum on such market value for the period commencing from the date of the publication of the notification under Section 4, till the date of the award of the Collector or the date of taking possession of the land, (Period during which proceedings held up due to stay or injunction order of Court , shall be excluded)
23(2)	Additional sum of [thirty per centum] on such market value, in consideration of the compulsory nature of the acquisition.(Solatium)
24	Matters to be neglected in determining compensation – *Degree of Urgency

	<p>*Disinclination to part with land</p> <p>*Damage sustained which if caused by Private person would not make him liable in Suit</p> <p>* Potential damage to land acquired (after Section 6 Declaration) as a consequence of use to which it will be put .</p> <p>*Increase in value of land acquired , likely to accrue form the use to which it will be put after acquisition</p> <p>* Increase in value of other land acquired , likely to accrue form the use to which it will be put after acquisition</p> <p>* Any outlay , improvements disposal of land without sanction of Collector after Section 4(1) Notification</p> <p>* Land put to use forbidden by law or opposed to public policy .</p>
25	Compensation Awarded by Court shall not be less than amount awarded by Collector (under Section 11) .
28	interest @ 9% on the Court awarding excess compensation , from the date the Collector took possession of land to the date of payment of such excess in Court. Where such excess or part thereof is paid after expiry of one year from the date possession is taken , Interest will be increased to fifteen per centum per annum as payable on the amount of such excess or part thereof , from the date of expiry of one year
28A	Redetermination of the Award by Collector in case of other persons aggrieved due to Section 4 Notification , on the basis of the Award of Court under Section 18
31(2)	Compensation may be deposited in Court , if person does not consent to receive it , dispute as to title or as to apportionment of compensation .
31(3)	Collector with sanction of Govt. instead of money make arrangement with person having limited interest in land , by grant of other lands in exchange or remission of land revenue on his other lands.
34	Collector's Liability – If amount of compensation not paid or deposited before taking possession of land , Interest @9%per annum from the date of possession till amount paid or deposited . If amount of compensation or part thereof not paid or deposited , after expiry of one year from the date of possession , Interest @15% shall be payable , from the expiry of said one year .
35 ,36	Temporary occupation of land not exceeding 3 years – compensation either in gross sum of money or by monthly or other periodical payments as may be agreed upon. On restoration , compensation for damage ,if any , done to land and not forming part of agreement .
Part VII Section 41	For acquisition of land for Companies, consent of Appropriate Govt. and execution of agreement necessary. The Agreement shall interalia provide for costs of acquisition payable to appropriate Govt.
48	If Govt. withdraws from acquisition , Collector shall determine the amount of compensation for damage in consequence of Notice, proceedings , costs incurred due to prosecution of proceedings .

**In the following matter Section 23 of the Act regarding compensation was in issue –
Supreme Court of India Yadavrao P. Pathade (Dead) By Lrs. ... vs State Of Maharashtra
on 24 January, 1996 observed thus -**

Received: 22 February 2024

Revised: 2 March 2024

Final Accepted 12 March 2024

38

“whether the appellants are entitled to payment of interest on solatium payable under Section 23(2) of the Land Acquisition Act(Act 1 of 1894)...

*“5...The legislation, therefore, made a distinction between compensation under Section 23(1) and the additional amount on such market value as solatium in consideration of compulsory nature of acquisition. In other words, **Section 28 does not comprehend payment of interest on solatium** when it expressly mentions payment of interest on compensation under Section 28 referable to Section 23(1) of the Act.”^x*

2.3. Various Policies were introduced not having statutory mandate -

***NEW National Policy On Resettlement And Rehabilitation For Project Affected Families 2003 which came into force w.e.f. February, 2004.**

***The National Rehabilitation And Resettlement Policy, 2007 came into force w.e.f. 31 October, 2007.**

2.4. Fair Compensation Under The Right To Fair Compensation And Transparency In Land Acquisition, Rehabilitation And Resettlement Act, 2013 –

Land Acquisition Rehabilitation and Resettlement (LARR) Bill 2011 . The bill was passed by Lok Sabha on 29/08/2013 and in Rajya Sabha on 4/09/2013 with amendments as approved. The Bill was passed with the title name as **“The Right to Fair Compensation and Transparency in Land Acquisition, Rehabilitation and Resettlement Act, 2013”** and came into effect on 1 January 2014.

TABLE II

COMPENSATION PROVISIONS IN NUTSHELL UNDER RFCT LARR ACT 2013 –

SECTION	PARTICULARS
Section 3 (i) and (u)	“Market value” (value determined as per Section 26) and “cost of acquisition” defined . Cost of acquisition includes amount of compensation which includes solatium , enhanced compensation ordered by land Acquisition and Rehabilitation and Resettlement Authority or Court, interest payable thereon any other amount determined as payable by Authority or Court .
Section 26	<p>Determination of Market value – Criteria –(a) Ready Reckoner rate (b) average sale price for similar type of land situated in nearest Village or nearest vicinity Area (c) compensation as agreed upon or consented in case of acquisition of land for Private companies or for PPP projects ; whichever is higher.</p> <p>Date of determination of market value is date of Notification under Section 11. S per Explanation 1 and 2 , average sale price is determined by taking into account the sale deeds or Agreements to registered during preceding three years sale and half of such documents recording highest Sale Price .</p> <p>Market value shall be multiplied by a factor as mentioned in Schedule I for rural or Urban Area as the case may be .</p> <p>As mentioned in subsection (3) the State Govt. shall specify the minimum floor price or minimum price per unit area of the Said Land .</p> <p>Shares as part compensation which shall not exceed 25% of market value Collector shall revise and update market value . Constitution provision[Article 30(1A)] for protection of religious and linguistic minorities has been incorporated</p>
27	Assets attached to land
28	<p>Parameters to be considered in determining the amount of compensation -* Market value under Section 26</p> <p>*Damage sustained –</p> <p>(a) Taking of any standing crops or trees (b) severing of such land from his other land</p>

	<p>© by reason of acquisition injuriously affecting his other property , movable or immovable or his earnings</p> <p>(d) reasonable expenses for the person compelled to change his residence or place of business</p> <p>(e) diminution of profits during the period between time of publication of Declaration under Section 19 and time of Collector’s taking possession of land</p> <p>(f) any other ground based on justice , equity , beneficial</p>
29	Determination of market value of the Building or other immovable property or assets attached to land or building , trees and plants , standing crops- use the services of experienced persons in the relevant field .
30 (1)	In addition to compensation , solatium equivalent to 100% of the compensation amount (Under Section 3(i) “amount of compensation includes solatium” then how is this to be harmoniously interpreted ?)
30(3)	Collector shall award amount @12% per annum on market value for the period between date of publication of Notification of SIA Study under Section 4(2) till date of Award of Collector or date of taking possession whichever is earlier . (Note – In case SIA Study exempted then what will be the fate of this amount ?)
Chapter V (31,32)	relate to rehabilitation and resettlement Award for affected families and provision of infrastructural Amenities in resettlement area by the Collector .
39	Additional compensation in case of multiple displacements .
40	Special Powers in case of urgency to acquire land by Collector where Collector has to tender 80% of the compensation before taking possession . An additional compensation of 75% is payable for land and property acquired.
41	Special provisions in case acquisition of land in Scheduled Area (for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes) . One third of the Compensation amount shall be paid as first installment and rest shall be paid after taking over the possession of land . Rehabilitation and resettlement benefits are compulsory . Fishing rights in the reservoir area of irrigation or hydel Projects to persons having fishing rights in river ,pond or am . In case they are located outside the district additional 25% of the Rehabilitation and resettlement benefits in monetary terms with a one time entitlement of Rs. 50,000/-

47	Obligations of Requiring body with regard to rehabilitation and resettlement can be quantified into monetary Amount .
69	Powers of Land Acquisition , Rehabilitation and Resettlement Authority to determine the amount of compensation and shall also award amount calculated at 12% per annum on market value from date of Notification under Section 11 till date of Award of Collector or till date of taking possession whichever is earlier . Proceedings held up on account of stay or injunction Order of the Court shall be excluded . Authority shall also award 100% Solatium over total compensation amount .
72	In case excess sum is awarded by Authority , Collector is directed to pay interest @ 9% on excess sum from the date he took possession of land to the date of payment of such excess to Authority .After expiry of one year from the date on which possession is taken , if excess amount or part thereof is not paid , then interest @15% will be chargeable from the date of expiry of said period of one year .
73	Where Authority allows compensation in excess of the amount awarded by Collector , then the Collector has to redetermine the amount in case of other persons aggrieved by the Award of the Collector , subject to their making applications to Collector within the prescribed period .
80	Where amount or compensation is not paid or deposited before taking possession of land , the Collector shall pay the amount with interest @ 9% from the date of taking possession till it is paid or deposited . If compensation or any part thereof is not paid or deposited within a period of one year from the date possession is taken interest @15% shall be payable from the date of expiry of said period of one year .
81,82	For temporary occupation of waste or arable land , the Collector shall pay compensation either in gross sum or monthly payments as agreed and on restoration , compensation for damage(if any) done to land and not provided for in agreement .
93	If the appropriate Govt. withdraws from acquisition , compensation payable for damage suffered by Owner as a result of Notice or other proceedings thereunder together with costs reasonably incurred in prosecution of the proceedings.

105	if ownership of land acquired is transferred to any person for a consideration amount , 40 % of the appreciated land value shall be shared amongst the persons from whom land was acquired or their legal heirs .
108	Unique Section under which affected families may at their option avail higher compensation and rehabilitation and resettlement under State Law or Policy instead of under 2013 Act .

Under Section 96 - *“No income tax or stamp duty shall be levied on any award or agreement made under this Act, except under section 46”* By virtue of Circular dated 25/10/2016 of Govt. of India , Ministry of Finance, Department of Revenue , Central Board of Direct Taxes(CBDT) , section 96 of RFCTLAAR Act has been clarified as *“Award or Agreement been exempted for levy of income tax vide Section 96 of RFCTLARR Act shall also not be taxable under the provisions of Income Tax Act 1961.”*

Under Section 46 – If Any person is purchasing land through private negotiations for an area equal to or exceeding the notified limits, for which the payment of Rehabilitation and Resettlement Costs is required, the provisions of Section 96 regarding exemption from income tax or stamp duty shall not be applicable .

As per Section 113(1) , and RFCTLAAR (Removal of Difficulties) Order, 2015 , provisions of RFCTLAAR Act, 2013 relating to determination of compensation (as per First Schedule) rehabilitation and resettlement (Second Schedule) , Infrastructure Amenities (Third Schedule) have been extended to land acquisition under various other legislations in Fourth Schedule of RFCTLAAR Act, 2013. However see judgment of Hon’ble **Supreme Court in [State of West Bengal Vs. Anindya Sundar Das and Ors. (2022 SCC Online SC 1382)]** that High Court was justified in coming to the conclusion that *“in the guise of removing the difficulties, the State cannot change the scheme and essential provisions of the Act.”*

Section 24 is for applicability of the Act for determination of compensation and lapsing of acquisition proceedings, which has been interpreted by the Hon’ble Supreme Court under Reference of Hon’ble Supreme Court (5 Judge Bench) in **S.L.P. (C) Nos.9036-9038 Of 2016) in Indore Development AuthorityPetitioner Versus Manoharlal & Ors. Etc.Respondent(S) With Connected Slps - Judgment – March 6 , 2020,interalia -**

- “ 1. Under the provisions of Section 24(1)(a) in case the award is not made as on 1.1.2014 the date of commencement of Act of 2013, there is no lapse of proceedings. Compensation has to be determined under the provisions of Act of 2013.
2. In case the award has been passed within the window period of five years, then proceedings shall continue under the Act of 1894 as if it has not been repealed.
3. “ The deemed lapse of land acquisition proceedings under Section 24(2) of the Act of 2013 takes place where due to inaction of authorities for five years or more prior to commencement of the said Act, the possession of land has not been taken nor compensation has been paid.”
4. “The consequence of non-deposit is provided in proviso to Section 24(2) ... In case the obligation under Section 31 of the Land Acquisition Act of 1894 has not been fulfilled, interest under Section 34 of the said Act can be granted. Non-deposit of compensation (in court) does not result in the lapse of land acquisition proceedings. In case of non-deposit with respect to the majority of holdings for five years or more, compensation under the Act of 2013 has to be paid to the "landowners" as on the date of notification for land acquisition under Section 4 of the Act of 1894.”
5. “Land owners who had refused to accept compensation or who sought reference for higher compensation, cannot claim that the acquisition proceedings had lapsed under Section 24(2) of the Act of 2013.”

The First Schedule relatable to Section 30(2) describes particulars and details of compensation for those whose lands are acquired and tenants referred in Section 3© in a proportion to be decided by the appropriate Govt.

TABLE III

SCHEDULE I- COMPENSATION COMPONENTS TO LAND OWNERS

TABLE IV

SCHEDULE II – ELEMENTS OF REHABILITATION UNDER 2013 ACT

Elements of Rehabilitation and Resettlement	Property lost /acquired, Entitlement, In lieu of Entitlement
PROVISION OF HOUSE IN CASE OF DISPLACEMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HOUSE IS LOST IN RURAL AREAS- constructed House , equivalent cost • HOUSE IS LOST IN URBAN AREA -Constructed House - Plinth Area 50 sq. mtrs., Financial Assistance (Rs. 1,50,000/-) • AFFECTED FAMILY WITHOUT HOMESTEAD RESIDING FOR THREE YEARS - do
LAND FOR LAND IRRIGATION PROJECT -IN LIEU OF COMPENSATION REDUCED TO STATUS OF MARGINA FARMER OR LANDLESS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • STATUS OF MARGINAL FARMER OR LANDLESS -One Acre land in command area , • SCHEDULED CASTES SCHEDULED TRIBES -land equivalent to land acquired or two and one half acres ,
OFFER FOR DEVELOPED LAND -	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LAND ACQUIRED FOR URBANISATION PURPOSES - 20% of developed land , equivalent amount from compensation package deducted
CHOICE OF ANNUITY OR EMPLOYMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AFFECTED FAMILIES - Employment to one member or Rs. 5,00,000/-or Annuity Policy for 20 years @ Rs 2000/- per month .
SUBSISTENCE GRANT FOR DISPLACED FAMILIES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DISPLACED FAMILY - Monthly subsistence allowance of Rs.3000/-per month for one year . • IF SCHEDULED CASTE AND TRIBE - Monthly subsistence allowance of Rs.3000/- per month for one year and Rs. 50000/-, relocated in similar ecological zone .
TRANSPORTATION COST FOR DISPLACED FAMILIES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DISPLACED FAMILY - One time financial assistance of Rs. 50,000/-
CATTLE SHED/PETTY SHOPS COST	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CATTLE OR PETTY SHOP-Financial Assistance Rs. 25000/-
ONE-TIME GRANT TO ARTISAN, SMALL TRADERS AND CERTAIN OTHERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARTISAN, SMALL TRADER OR SELF-EMPLOYED PERSON OR AN AFFECTED FAMILY WHICH OWNED NON AGRICULTURAL LAND OR COMMERCIAL, INDUSTRIAL OR INSTITUTIONAL STRUCTURE-SHOP-Financial Assistance Rs. 25000/-
FISHING RIGHTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IRRIGATION OR HYDEL PROJECTS, THE AFFECTED FAMILIES-Fishing rights in Reservoirs
ONE-TIME RESETTLEMENT ALLOWANCE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EACH AFFECTED FAMILY- Rs. 50,000/-
STAMP DUTY AND REGISTRATION FEE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PAYABLE FOR REGISTRATION OF THE LAND OR HOUSE ALLOTTED-Borne by requiring body , The land for house allotted (a) shall be free from all encumbrances. • (b) may be in the joint names of wife and husband

Received: 22 February 2024
Revised: 2 March 2024
Final Accepted 12 March 2024

3. Modifications in Maharashtra State Acts of Land Acquisition-*** Maharashtra State Amendment Act 2018 (Amending Central Act Of 2013) -**

- Agreement on matters to be included in award(Section 23A).
- Exclusion of Time Period in case of Injunction etc.(Section 24A)

* Lump Sum Amount in lieu of Rehabilitation And Resettlement Scheme in certain cases (Section 31A)

* Maharashtra State Acts relating to land acquisition exempted from applicability of RFCT LARR Act 2013 (Section 105A, Schedule V of the Maharashtra Amendment Act 2018)-These are mainly Four Acts - The Maharashtra Highways Act (LV of 1955), The Maharashtra Industrial Development Act, 1961 (Mah. III of 1962), The Maharashtra Regional and Town Planning Act, 1966 (Mah. XXXVII of 1966), The Maharashtra Housing and Area Development Act, 1976 (Mah. XXVIII of 1977)

* In these Schedule V Acts certain provisions relating to determination of Compensation and rehabilitation and resettlement under Schedule I, II and III of RFCT LARR Act got incorporated by way of Amendments . These amendments are -

- (a) Maharashtra Highways (Amendment) Act, 2018.(27 July 2018) –A new section 19B added
- (b) Maharashtra Industrial Development (Amendment) Act, 2019. (23/07/2019)
- (c) Maharashtra Regional Town Planning Act - On and from 29th August 2015, the 2013 Act applies to a "limited extent" to acquisitions under the MRTP Act.
- (d) In the Maharashtra Housing and Area Development Act, 1976 no such amendment incorporating provisions of 2013 Act , carried out .

All this has resulted in dilution of RFCT LARR Act 2013 .

Courts have interpreted this as limited Applicability of RFCT LARR Act 2013 and Doctrine of Incorporation was introduced .

4. Interpretation of legislation with respect to Compensation by Courts

Analysis of the Supreme Court Judgments and Bombay High Court Judgments from the year 2014 till 2023 on compensation under Central Law and Maharashtra State Law on land Acquisition has given a Kaleidoscope of varied pleas and principles in judgments viz. Doctrine of Reference , Doctrine of incorporation , limited applicability of 2013 Act to Maharashtra State Acts , delay in compensation , inadequate compensation , plea of paucity of funds by acquiring body , conflicting judgments , many a times for doing complete justice , the Hon'ble Supreme Court has to invoke Art. 142 of the Constitution .

TABLE V

SOME PRECEDENTS RELATING TO COMPENSATION UNDER LAND ACQUISITION LAW (SUPREME COURT OF INDIA)-

S. No.	Case Details	Crux/Ratio
1	SC- Central Warehousing Corporation ... Appellant(s); <i>Versus</i> , Thakur Dwara Kalan ul-Maruf Baraglan Wala (Dead) and Others ... Respondent(s).Civil Appeal Nos. of 2023 (Arising out of SLP (C) Nos. 30817-30818 of 2016),Decided on October 19, 2023	“The law on the point of annual increase whether on cumulative basis or non-cumulative basis and the rate of annual increase –Period to be applied is a major factor to be considered”– Gap of 11 years- 8% annual increase with cumulative effect applied after discussing Cases viz. . <i>Rameshbhai Jivanbhai Patel</i> , Also cases viz. <i>Ashrafi</i> , <i>Narbadi Devi</i> , <i>Ramrao Shankar Tapase</i> etc. were discussed . ^{xi}
2	SC- R.B. Dealers (P) Ltd. v. Metro Railway, Kolkata, (2019) 20 SCC 658 : 2019 SCC OnLine SC 871 at page 662, 663	“ <i>solatium amount to be determined and calculated under sub-section (1) of Section 30 of the 2013 Act shall ... shall not include an amount calculated at the rate of 12% p.a. on such market value payable under sub-section (3) of Section 30 of the 2013 Act.</i> ” ^{xii}
3	SC- Union of India v. Tarsem Singh, (2019) 9 SCC 304 : (2019) 4 SCC (Civ) 364 : 2019 SCC OnLine SC 1230 at page 322,325,330,332, decided on 19 th September 2019 .	“Constitutional validity of the 1997 Amendment in National Highways Act by which Solatium and interest removed- both before the 1997 Amendment Act and after the coming into force of the 2013 Act(pursuant to Notification dated 28-8-2015 issued under Section 105 read with Section 113 of the 2013 Act) , solatium and interest is payable to landowners, ...would not receive the protective umbrella of Article 31-C and, therefore, any infraction of Article 14 can be enquired into by Court.” ^{xiii}

4	<p>SC- State Of Maharashtra & Anr vs Basantibai Mohanlal Khetan & Ors . Decided on 13 March, 1986,</p>	<p>The Hon’ble SC observed that there are different methods of valuation based on classification having regard to <i>“the difference in the potentialities of the two types of lands”</i> ...<i>The method of capitalization is also one of the recognised methods ...”</i> The Hon’ble Court observed –<i>“ We fail to see any hostile discrimination in the instant case which will make sub-section (3) and sub-section (4) of section 44 of the Act (Maharashtra Housing and Development Act, 1976) violative of Article 14 of the Constitution merely because in the case of lands in municipal area all the methods of valuation under the Land Acquisition Act are not made available. ...”</i> The Court observed , <i>“The Act is brought into force to implement the directive principle contained in Article 39(b) and hence even if there is any infraction of Article 14 it is cured by Article 31C. ... Land ceiling laws, law providing for acquisition of land for providing housing accommodation, laws imposing ceiling on urban property etc. cannot (be) struck down by invoking Article 21 of the Constitution....”</i> ^{xiv}</p>
5	<p>SC - P. Vajravelu Mudaliar vs Special Deputy Collector, Madras & Anr Decided on 5 October, 1964</p>	<p>Analysing Article 32 (1) as amended by Constitution 4th Amendment Act 1955 , the Hon’ble Supreme Court observed that prior to 4th amendment <i>“a person whose land was acquired was entitled to compensation i.e., a "just equivalent" of the land of which he was deprived. ...”</i> The Court further observed that after amendment - <i>“If the question pertains to the adequacy of compensation, it is not justiciable; if the compensation fixed or the principles evolved for fixing it disclose that the legislature made the law in fraud of powers in the sense we have explained, the question is within the jurisdiction of the Court. ...”</i>^{xv}</p>

TABLE VI

SOME PRECEDENTS RELATING TO COMPENSATION UNDER LAND ACQUISITION LAW (BOMBAY HIGH COURT) -

Serial No.	Case details	Crux/Ratio
1	<p>HC- Rajeev Kumar Damodarprasad Bhadani–Versus Executive Engineer, Maharashtra State Electricity Distribution</p>	<p>Facts - Possession of the land had been taken without paying any compensation. Delay of 40 years in approaching the Court . Held - The State cannot evade its responsibility to pay the compensation merely on grounds of delay and laches. <i>“ The State cannot, on the ground of delay and laches, evade its</i></p>

Received: 22 February 2024

Revised: 2 March 2024

Final Accepted 12 March 2024

	Company Limited (MSEDCL)–Decided On : January 2024	<i>responsibility towards those from whom private property has been expropriated”^{xvi}</i>
2	Justices B P Colabawalla and M M Sathaye Sandesh Vitthal Thakur and Others Vs. the Deputy Collector , (Land Acquisition) , Raigad and others with Interim Application No. 1515 of 2023 and connected Writ Petitions , Decided 16 January 2024	Facts – Land acquired for MTHL (Mumbai Trans Harbour Sea Link) Atal Setu Project by invoking urgency clause under Section 17 of 1894 Act. Neither compensation paid nor possession taken till filing of Petitions . Held – There is no compliance of Section 17(3-A) (payment of 80% compensation before taking possession) – The land does not vest absolutely with the State and hence if Award is not passed within the Statutory period required by Law (before the new 2013 law came into force or even within a year after that,) the present acquisition proceedings had clearly lapsed. ...Land Owners who lost land will be entitled to compensation by passing of fresh Award by the State as per 2013 Act, ^{xvii}
	HC- Vijay and Others <i>Versus</i> State of Maharashtra, through Secretary, Urban Development Department and Another and connected petitions , Decided on July 8, 2022.	Determination of Compensation - MRTP Act – Land Acquisition Act 1894- RFCT LARR Act 2013- Interplay - Section 21(4) and consequently Section 22 of the LA Act of 2013, are not mandatory but directory in nature. For the said reasons, no direction can be issued to authorities <i>“to also determine rehabilitation and resettlement entitlements of the petitioners.”^{xviii}</i>
3	HC- Writ Petition No. 2698 of 2021, Dhangir Pandurang Gosavi <i>Versus</i> State of Maharashtra and Others Decided on February 10, 2021)	Held – <i>“8. In the case of Chimanlal Hargovinddas v. Special Land Acquisition Officer, Poona, (supra)” the Supreme Court has observed that in a Reference under Section 18 of the Old Act 1894 , Reference Court has to follow 13 principles as mentioned in Para 4(1) of that case .</i> <i>“9....In almost all the Land Acquisition References, which are subject matter of the present writ petitions, the learned Judges of the respective Reference Courts suo moto gone through the award and sale instances relied upon by the Land Acquisition Officers even though the said sale</i>

		<i>instances are not produced and proved before the Reference Courts.” Hence References not decided on merits . Hence judgments and orders of Reference Courts set aside .^{xix}</i>
4	HC-Pune Municipal Corporation <i>Versus</i> Rajeev L. Sangtani and others ,Civil Rev. Appln. No. 316 of 2016,Decided on August 7, 2019	Held -. Section 24(1)(a) of 2013 Act - ... <i>Expression “all provisions of this Act relating to determination of compensation ” does not envisage application of provisions contained in sections 26 to 30 of Act only- “adding thereto the amount calculated @ 12% per annum under section 69(2) and solatium of 100% over the total compensation amount.”^{xx}</i>
5	HC- Reliance Natural Resources Ltd., Mumbai and Another <i>Versus</i> State of Maharashtra and Others ,W.P. No. 572 of 2019, Decided on May 2, 2019	Held – “17... <i>If the words, “all provisions of this Act relating to the determination of compensation” (in Section 24(1)(a)2013 Act) are constructed in accordance with their natural, ordinary and popular sense, they indicate in clear and unequivocal terms that the provisions of the New Act 2013 relating to determination of compensation only apply and not all the provisions of the New Act, 2013. ... ”(Paras 17, 18, 22 and 23).^{xxi}</i> Provisions relating to rehabilitation and resettlement will not be applicable .
6	HC-(Aurangabad Bench) Bharat Sanchar Nigam Ltd , Osmanabad <i>Versus</i> Purushottam Martandarao Deshmukh (Died) Through Legal Heirs; Date of Decision: 24 April 2019	Maharashtra Regional and Town Planning Act, 1966, Section 126-Land Acquisition Act, 1894, Section 4- Rental compensation cannot be awarded in land acquisition proceeding, but for recovery of rental compensation the claimant has to approach the appropriate authorities under law. ^{xxii}

	<p>Bench: Sunil P. Deshmukh, P. R. Bora, Bombay High Court, Bharat Sanchar Nigam Limited, Osmanabad Vs. State of Maharashtra, The Collector Osmanabad, Purushottam S/o Martandrao Deshmukh, Decided on 31 January, 2018</p> <p>Also see - 2016 SCC OnLine Bom 16063, (BEFORE <u>B.P. DHARMADHIKARI</u> AND <u>KU. INDIRA JAIN, JJ.</u>), Arvind Shreenivas Bobde (Dead) through Legal Heirs, <i>Versus</i>, State of Maharashtra, Writ Petition No. 1954 of 2001, Decided on June 13, 2016</p>	<p>Issue – <i>“the legality, propriety and validity of order dated 04-10-2006 passed by respondent no. 2 - Collector, Osmanabad, requiring the petitioner to pay rental compensation as awarded under the order.”</i></p> <p>Observations - Govt. Resolution dated 01-12-1972 for working out yearly rental compensation for occupation of land without acquisition .</p> <p><i>“the petitioner has been in possession of the land in question since 1994 continuously without any interruption and that even before land acquisition proceedings were initiated with notification, certain developments at its instance had taken place.”^{xxiii}</i></p> <p>Request declined that liability of payment of Rental Compensation is upon Respondents. Claimant entitled to Rental compensation as possession taken much prior to Section 4(1) Notification.</p>
<p>7</p>	<p>Bombay High Court (Nagpur Bench) - Hardas (Haridas) S/O Ramdas Udasi ... vs The State Of Maharashtra, Thr, Writ Petition No. 1461 Of 2018, on 10 April, 2019.) -</p>	<p>Held – <i>“24. In view of the observations of the Apex Court in the judgments [Ram Chand v. Union of India, Vishwas Namdeo Devare v. State of Maharashtra, in Writ Petition No. 430 of 2009 delivered on 28-2-2019 [2019 MhLJ Online 3] and the concept of ‘just compensation’ in case of compulsory acquisition of private land for public purpose by applying extraordinary power of ‘Eminent Domain’, it would be a gross abuse of powers if the impugned Award is allowed to be sustained on the basis of market value which was prevailing 22 years back.... The respondent is directed to initiate fresh inquiry for assessment of compensation on the basis of the provisions of the Act of 2013 by taking 1-1-2014 as the date of section 19 Notification of the Act of 2013 and pay compensation to the petitioner as expeditiously as possible”^{xxiv}</i></p>

	<p>High Court of Bombay at Goa-(Mohini T. Gad and Others ,<i>Versus</i> Deputy Collector, Land Acquisition Officer ,First Appeal No. 87 of 2015,Decided on October 5, 2018.)</p>	<p>Facts- The dates of declaration of public notices under Section 4 of the Land Acquisition Act were 12 June 2006 and 14 August 2008. The notification was published under Section 6 of the Act on 3 August 2009.The Land Acquisition Officer rendered an award on 5 July 2010 and the possession was taken on 10 August 2010. In Reference before Court , the Appellants relied upon a comparable sale instance(Sale Deed dated 3/05/2010) of a property situated in the same locality and though it was after the relevant date, it was a germane piece of evidence to determine the correct market value. The Appellants also relied upon an award dated 13 August 1996 which according to the Appellants was in respect of the property located in the same area and it was comparable.</p> <p>Held – “4....<i>Not only there is no satisfactory discussion(by District Judge in Reference) , but the learned District Judge has reproduced the facts not of the present reference but of the award which was cited as evidence by the Appellants.... ”</i></p> <p>“5. <i>There is a complete non-application of mind. These are not the facts of the present reference at all.</i>”</p> <p>The Judgment and Award quashed and set aside .The Land Acquisition case restored to the file of District Court .^{xxv}</p>
8	<p>Sidhu Jaiwanta Jare <i>Versus</i> State of Maharashtra, 26/06/2018</p>	<p>Post notification sale deeds produced for determination of market value cannot be considered.^{xxvi}</p>
9	<p>HC- State of Maharashtra [Through the Special Land Acquisition Officer, Nashik] <i>Versus</i> Gopal Kalu Udar and Others ,First Appeal</p>	<p>Amendment to 1894 Act -by Amending Act No. 68 of 1984 with effect from 24th September, 1984 – Beneficial provisions-Section 23(1A) – (additional component at the rate of 12% p.a. of the market value) Section 23(2) –(the amount of solatium was increased from 15% to 30%.) , Section 34 – (the rate of interest was also increased from 6% to 9% for the first year after taking possession of the land, and 15% beyond the period of one year after taking possession till the payment of compensation amount) – Review Application</p>

	No. 624 of 1994,Decided on May 9, 2017	maintainable if Award was not passed or compensation not paid prior to coming into force of amendment Act; (Award was passed and amount of compensation was received by claimants after cut off date of 30 th April, 1982(date of introduction of Amendment Bill) - Amendment Act will have Application) . ^{xxvii}
10	ABA s/o Dashrath Pawar Versus State of Maharashtra and another, Decided on September 22, 2016	Reference Court granted enhanced compensation and interest under Section 28 and 34 of the Act of 1894 . However interest not granted on amount payable to appellants under sections 23(1-A) and 23(2) . Appellant entitled to get interest on aggregate amount of compensation from the date of Award and not from date of possession . ^{xxviii}
11	Gangadhar Nanaji Milmile, Versus Western Coalfields Ltd., Nagpur ,F.A. Nos. 45, 47, 48 and 56 to 59 of 2005, Decided on May 2, 2016	<i>Held – “ Sub-section (3) of section 17 (Coal Bearing Areas Act) makes entitlement to interest only at the rate of five per centum per annum from the time the compensation becomes due, until it shall have been so paid or deposited. If the provision of the Circular dated 12th February, 1986 is to be construed as making applicable the amended provision of section 34 of the Land Acquisition Act to the cases of acquisition under the Coal Bearing Areas Act, it shall clearly run contrary to the provisions of sub-section (3) of section 17 of the said Act. The field is already occupied and unless the provision of section 17 of the said Act is amended, the circular would not confer the benefit of nine per cent and fifteen per cent interest, as contemplated by section 34 of the Land Acquisition Act. The claimants are therefore, not entitled to interest in terms of section 34 of the Land Acquisition Act. ”^{xxix}</i>
12	2016 SCC OnLine Bom 2236, (BEFORE B.P. DHARMADHIKARI, <u>R.K. DESHPANDE</u> AND P.N. DESHMUKH, JJ.),State of Maharashtra ,Versus Kailash Shiva Rangari ,F.A. No. 251 of 2003,Decided on April 18, 2016	Reference Answered - <i>33. “(a) If the possession is taken before the notification under section 4(1) of the Land Acquisition Act is published and/or before the award is passed, the landowner would be entitled for interest as per section 34 necessarily from the date of passing of the award under section 11 of the said Act, except in cases where the possession is taken in accordance with section 17 of the said Act, and in that situation only, the provision of section 34 of the said Act shall start operating from the date of possession.”^{xxx}</i>
13	HC-Purushottam Dattulal Paldiwal, R/o Paldiwal Hospital, Giripeth, Amravati Road, Nagpur-440 010 Versus 1. State	Case is, concerned with the payment of compensation under sub-section (2) of Section 48 of the Land Acquisition Act for withdrawal of acquisition.

	of Maharashtra, through Special Land Acquisition Officer, and Other , Decided on 21/11/2015	Held – “In view of withdrawal of land in question from acquisition, the claimant is neither entitled for solatium nor for compensation for severance of the land....” The notification under Section 4 of the Land Acquisition Act is equivalent to the notification under subsection (1) of Section 31 of the Maharashtra Town & Planning Act. ^{xxxii}
14	HC-State of Maharashtra and others <i>Versus</i> Namdeo s/o Champat Kshirsagar Decided on June 11, 2015	Held - Sale instance of a house property on an extremely small plot of 1134 sq. feet in village cannot be considered for deciding price of a large tract of land situated outside village(5 Hectares in present case) . ^{xxxiii}
15	Panjabrao s/o Ganpatrao Borade <i>Versus</i> State of Maharashtra and others ,W.P. No. 4274 of 2014, Decided on March 9, 2015	Held – “ <i>The basic reason which seems to be considered for providing higher multiplier factor even up to two for lands situated in rural area sought to be acquired for the project is dependence of the people on such land for their survival and livelihood, coupled with low market price of such remotely located land, as compared to land situated in urban area. extraneous consideration of inadequacy of funds and in viable increase in budgetary cost vitiates the exercise of discretion conferred upon the appropriate Government under the First Schedule to the Act of 2013.</i> ” ^{xxxiii}
16	Tukaram <i>Versus</i> State of Maharashtra, Through Government Pleader, High Court of Bombay and Others , Decided on December 15, 2014	Held -Possession lost before Section 4 Notification , Benefits under Section 34 of the Act not available . “ <i>benefit of Section 23(1A) also should have been declined.</i> ”[Reference - Land Acquisition Officer v. Ramkrishna Reddy [(2011) 11 SCC 648] and Dinkar Sandipan Gholve State of Maharashtra [(2009) 3 Bom CR 891] ^{xxxiv}
17	Datta Rao s/o Kerbarao Deshmukh and others ... <i>Versus</i> State of Maharashtra and others. W.P. No. 7540 of 2011 Decided on February 24, 2014	Land Acquisition Act, S. 28-A — Compensation for acquired land — Redetermination of — Maintainability of successive application — Application under section 28-A to be filed within 90 days from date of first award — Any further award in respect of same acquisition would not provide any fresh cause of action to file successive application. Award under section 28-A (2) is on par with Award under section 11 so far provisions of reference under section 11 are concerned . Land Acquisition Act SS. 11, 18, 34 and Civil Procedure Code, S. 35 — Compensation for acquired land — Award made on 2-5-2011— Acquiring body not deposited amount of

		compensation till January, 2014 - Interest to be paid till date of deposit of compensation — State Government is primarily liable to pay compensation as sub-section (1) of section 31 enjoins Collector to offer compensation — Liability of State Government and 4th respondent-MKV Development Corporation will be joint and several. ^{xxxv}
18	HC- Sushma Murlidhar Ghadge & Another vs The State Of Maharashtra & Others, Writ Petition No. 4121/2013 with connected Petitions ,Decided on 13 December, 2013	<u>Maharashtra Industrial Development Act -.</u> Held – “10...Once there is a lawful agreement contemplated by Sub-section (3A) of Section 33 of the MID Act, the Collector is under an obligation to make an award directing payment of compensation in terms of the agreement. On this aspect, the scheme of the said Act is completely different from the Land Acquisition Act, 1894....” Directions given for payment of interest on unpaid compensation from respective dates of written Agreements @ of “maximum rate of interest paid by the State Bank of India on the fixed deposits as of 2010.”(Para 16) ^{xxxvi}

4. CONCLUSION

* To determine compensation some uniform modalities/guidelines shall be prepared by the Central Government and it should be left to the State Governments to build statutory provisions around them without traversing their boundaries to ensure overall uniformity in Statutes throughout the Country .

* Market Value is defined but compensation is not defined in the 2013 Act though under Section 3(i) “cost of acquisition” is defined which in subclause (i) gives an inclusive definition of “amount of compensation” . Lack of clarity in definition is leading to conflicting judgments . A clarity either in statutory terms or policy of the Central Government touching every aspect of compensation is necessary so that compensation can be determined at the initial rung in the hierarchy with perfect accuracy . This will also help in avoiding unnecessary litigation .

* As per observation of the Report (1994-1995) on the Land Acquisition Act, 1894 of the Standing Committee (10th Lok Sabha) “the different formulae are adopted by different State

Governments to arrive at the market value and in the absence of clear cut guidelines/provisions the persons whose land is acquired by the Government do not get the due compensation.” The principles for determination of compensation shall be simple and uniform.

* Often the plea is raised by the acquiring body of paucity of funds . For eg.the Hon’ble Bombay High Court in **Trimbak Joma Thakur (Since Deceased) Through His LRS and Heirs Dashrath Trimbak Thakur and Others ... Petitioners Versus Principal Secretary, Urban Development Department and Others ... Respondents (Decided on April 29, 2022)** has observed – *“68. There is no substance in the submissions of CIDCO that there is a shortage of funds or that the funds are required for several projects and on that ground CIDCO is unable to deposit any amount insofar as these petitioners are concerned. The entire action on the part of CIDCO for not depositing the amount is in gross violation of Article 14 and 300-A of the Constitution of India.”* ^{xxxvii} The Act and Rules are already providing for payment of compensation prior to Award or taking over of possession , but these need to be implemented in letter and spirit for giving compensation to the affected persons promptly . The Standing Committee had recommended creation of Special contingency fund in this regard which is a relevant suggestion in the present Scenario also .^{xxxviii}

* States have their own criteria for valuation of land /trees /movable/immovable properties. For eg. In **Bhikubee w/o Anwar Shah Versus State of Maharashtra and another** (Decided on January 22, 2014)^{xxxix} the Hon’ble Bombay High Court has stated – *“Special Land Acquisition Officer awarded compensation of only 200 fruit trees with assumption that 100 fruit trees may not get yield. Such assumption is without any base and is merely a surmise — It has caused prejudice to claimant who lost his property/land ”* Definite principles for valuation of assets shall be evolved as a matter of policy so that the affected person gets fair compensation and is not compelled to rush to Authority or Court for higher compensation . This will remove the burden and losses to Public Exchequer arising due to payment of interest / additional compensation awarded by Authority /Court due to incorrect decisions of Land acquisition Authorities .

* The reference date for computation of the amount of compensation in cases of acquisition of land are different in Central and State Laws which is breeding discrimination . As per Central Govt. explanation *“The reference date for calculation of market value, under section 24(1)(a) should be 01.01.2014 ...in any case of land acquisition proceedings initiated under the Land Acquisition Act, 1894, where no Award under section 11 of the said Land Acquisition Act has been made”* In all such cases under Maharashtra Acts relating to land acquisition , the

reference date may be kept as 1/01/2014 to bring uniformity . In other cases the date of determining the market value can be the date of taking possession of the Land .

* Legal proceedings are expensive and not affordable . As per Section 46 of the Maharashtra Court Fees Act, the State has the power to reduce and remit the court fees. The said power can be exercised by the State to exempt or fix nominal fixed court-fee, in land acquisition matters , instead of ad-valorem court fee. Invariably the matters go for reference for enhancement of compensation . As has been stated by the Hon'ble Supreme Court in the case of **Shri Ambya Kalya Mhatre through LRs v. The State of Maharashtra** in Civil Appeal No. 7784 of 2011 [Arising out of SLP [c] No. 20741 of 2009] decided on 12.09.2011-*“Most of the land owners are agriculturist. For many of them, the only source of livelihood is taken away by the acquisition of their lands. ...the amount awarded by the Collector being comparatively small, the requirement to pay ad-valorem court-fee on the application causes irreparable hardship, forcing the land loser to seek a lesser increase than what is warranted.”*

* The Hon'ble Supreme Court in **the Central Warehousing Corporation vs Thakur Dwara Kalan Ul-Maruf Baragan** has stated that in determining the market value, *“the consistent view taken by this Court for awarding annual increase to determine the just compensation varies from case to case and the period to be applied is a major factor to be considered.”* The Hon'ble Court discussed various precedents for eg. “Subhash Chander” (2023) where it was held that annual increase could vary from 8% to 15% per year. In the case of Rameshbhai Jivanbhai Patel (supra) and other similar matters, annual increase cumulatively at the rate of 12% for a period of three years was awarded . It is suggested if Ready Recknor Rates are updated and revised every year for every location and area , actual enhancement of rate every year can be calculated easily even at the level of quasi judicial body like Land Acquisition Officer . The Ready Recknor rates shall be a live document and shall not be freezed for any year .

* The Law should balance between private and Public interests , a generous compensation regime for the persons interested will increase costs of the Govt. or acquiring body however at the same time it may mitigate defiance by persons affected to a particular Project , which will reduce litigation , delay and inflationary costs .

REFERENCES

- ⁱ (BEFORE M.S. SONAK, J.), In the High Court of Bombay, Civil Appellate Jurisdiction, State of Maharashtra *Versus* Smt. Sharadabai Ganesh Oze ... Respondent; First Appeal No. 208 of 1992 With Civil Application No. 2995 of 1992 With connected Appeals , Decided on April 3, 2017.) , (2017 SCC OnLine Bom 1697)
- ⁱⁱ Constituent Assembly Debates
- ⁱⁱⁱ Supreme Court , Bench: M. Patanjali Sastri, Mehr Chand Mahajan, Ghulam Hasan, B. Jagannadhadas, SUDHI RANJAN, The State of West Bengal Vs Mrs. Bela Banerjee and others on 11 December 1953.
- ^{iv} Supreme Court , Bench -Sastri, M. Patanjali (Cj), Mahajan, Mehr Chand, Das, Sudhi Ranjan, Hasan, Ghulam, Jagannadhadas, B., The State Of West Bengal Vs. Mrs. Bela Banerjee And Others, 11 Dec. 1953
- ^v P Suresh Babu , Comparative Analysis of Land Acquisition and Rehabilitation Policies Across India – A Comparative Study about Maharashtra and Uttara Pradesh, Journal of Advances in Economics and Business Management p-ISSN: 2394-1545; e-ISSN: 2394-1553; Volume-7, Issue-4; October-December, 2020 pp. 13-18 © Krishi Sanskriti Publications <http://www.krishisanskriti.org/Publication.html>
- ^{vi} Rai M. N. Gupta Bahadur , Land Acquisition Acts and Principles of Evaluation , S.C. Sarkar and Sons Ltd. , 1/1/1-C, College Square , Calcutta , 1939, P.136.
- ^{vii} Romer J ., Bombay High Court, Sri Raja Vyricherla Narayana ... vs The Revenue Divisional Officer on 23 February, 1939
- ^{viii} Supreme Court of India , Bench: Sinha, Bhuvneshwar P.(Cj), Subbarao, K., Ayyangar, N. Rajagopala, Mudholkar, J.R., Aiyar, T.L. Venkatarama in Smt. Somavanti And Others vs The State Of Punjab And Others (Equivalent citations: 1963 AIR 151, 1963 SCR (3) 774) on 2 May, 1962, Equivalent citations: 1963 AIR 151, 1963 SCR (3) 774
- ^{ix} The Land Acquisition Act 1894 (as modified upto 1st September 1985)
- ^x Bench: K Ramaswamy, S Ahmed, G Pattanaik, Supreme Court of India Yadavrao P. Pathade (Dead) By Lrs. ... vs State Of Maharashtra on 24 January, 1996 Equivalent citations: JT 1996 (2) SC 240, 1996 (4) KarLJ 666, 1996 (1) KLT 452 SC, 1996 (2) SCALE 96, (1996) 2 SCC 570, 1996 1 SCR 965
- ^{xi} (BEFORE VIKRAM NATH AND AHSANUDDIN AMANULLAH, JJ.),CeCentral Warehousing Corporation ... Appellant(s);*Versus*, Thakur Dwara Kalan ul-Maruf Baraglan Wala (Dead) and Others ... Respondent(s).Civil Appeal Nos. of 2023 (Arising out of SLP (C) Nos. 30817-30818 of 2016),Decided on October 19, 2023, **2023 SCC OnLine SC 1361.**

^{xii} Bench: Arun Mishra, S. Abdul Nazeer, M.R. Shah, Supreme Court of India, *Rb Dealers Private Limited vs The Metro Railway Kolkatta*, Decided on 17 July, 2019, AIR 2019 SUPREME COURT 3447

^{xiii} Bench: Surya Kant, R.F. Nariman, Supreme Court of India, *Union Of India vs Tarsem Singh*, decided on 19 September, 2019, Air 2019 Supreme Court 4689

^{xiv} Bench: E.S. Venkataramiah, M.P. Thakkar, Supreme Court of India, *State Of Maharashtra & Anr vs Basantibai Mohanlal Khetan & Ors*, decided on 13 March, 1986, 1986 AIR 1466

^{xv} Bench: Subbarao K., K.N. Wanchoo, M. Hidayatullah, Raghubar Dayal, S.M. Sikri, Supreme Court of India, *P. Vajravelu Mudaliar vs Special Deputy Collector, Madras & Anr*. decided on 5 October, 1964, 1965 AIR 1017.

^{xvi} B. P. Colabawalla, Somasekhar Sundaresan JJ, Bombay High Court, *Rajeev Kumar Damodarprasad Bhadani Versus Executive Engineer, Maharashtra State Electricity Distribution Company Limited (MSEDCL) (earlier 'MSEB')*, Decided On : January 2024

^{xvii} Justices B P Colabawalla and M M Sathaye, Bombay High Court, *Sandesh Vitthal Thakur and Others Vs. the Deputy Collector, (Land Acquisition), Raigad and others with Interim Application No. 1515 of 2023 and connected Writ Petitions*, Decided 16 January 2024

^{xviii} (BEFORE SUNIL B. SHUKRE AND ANIL S. KILOR, JJ.), In the High Court of Bombay, Writ Petition No. 2012 of 2021, *Vijay and Others ... Petitioners Versus State of Maharashtra, through Secretary, Urban Development Department and Another ... Respondents and connected petitions*, Decided on July 8, 2022, 2022 SCC OnLine Bom 1488

^{xix} (BEFORE V.K.JADHAV,J.), , In the High Court of Bombay, *Dhangir Pandurang Gosavi Versus State of Maharashtra and Others*, Writ Petition No. 2698 of 2021, Decided on February 10, 2021), (2021 SCC OnLine Bom 6413

^{xx} (BEFORE R.M. BORDE, RAJESH G. KETKAR AND N.J. JAMADAR, JJ.), In the High Court of Bombay(Bombay) *Pune Municipal Corporation Versus Rajeev L. Sangtani and others*, Civil Rev. Appln. No. 316 of 2016, Decided on August 7, 2019, 2019 SCC OnLine Bom 1492

^{xxi} BEFORE R.M. BORDE AND N.J. JAMADAR, JJ.), In the High Court of Bombay,(*Reliance Natural Resources Ltd., Mumbai and Another Versus State of Maharashtra and Others*, W.P. No. 572 of 2019, Decided on May 2, 2019, 2019 SCC OnLine Bom 752.

^{xxii} Sunil K Kotwal J. High Court Of Bombay (Aurangabad Bench) *Bharat Sanchar Nigam Ltd, Osmanabad Versus Purushottam Martandarao Deshmukh (Died) Through Legal Heirs; State Of Maharashtra; Sub-Divisional Officer And Land Acquisition Officer, Bhoom, - Osmanabad*, Date of Decision: 24 April 2019, Citation: 2019 LawSuit(Bom) 680

^{xxiii} Bench: Sunil P. Deshmukh, P. R. Bora, Bombay High Court, *Bharat Sanchar Nigam Limited, Osmanabad Vs. State of Maharashtra, The Collector Osmanabad, Purushottam S/o Martandarao Deshmukh*, Decided on 31 January, 2018

^{xxiv} Bench: SUNIL B. SHUKRE & PUSHPA V. GANEDIWALA, JJ. Bombay High Court (Nagpur Bench), *Hardas (Haridas) S/O Ramdas Udasi ... vs The State Of Maharashtra*, Writ Petition No. 1461 Of 2018, on 10 April, 2019.)

^{xxv} (BEFORE N.M. JAMDAR AND PRITHVIRAJ K. CHAVAN, JJ.), In the High Court of Bombay at Goa, *Mohini T. Gad and Others, Versus Deputy Collector, Land Acquisition Officer, First Appeal No. 87 of 2015*, Decided on October 5, 2018., (2018 SCC OnLine Bom 3024).

Received: 22 February 2024

Revised: 2 March 2024

Final Accepted 12 March 2024

60

- xxvi 2018 SCC onLine Bom 1307, Sidhu S/O Jaiwanta Jare *Versus* State of Maharashtra, 26/06/2018
- xxvii SHALINI PHANSALKAR-JOSHI, J., State of Maharashtra [Through the Special Land Acquisition Officer, Nashik] *Versus* Gopal Kalu Udar and Others ,First Appeal No. 624 of 1994,Decided on May 9, 2017, 2017 SCC OnLine Bom 770.
- xxviii (BEFORE P.R. BORA, J.),ABA s/o Dashrath Pawar *Versus* State of Maharashtra and another ,F.A. Nos. 2526, 2529 and 2530 of 2016 ,Decided on September 22, 2016, 2016 SCC OnLine Bom 8777
- xxix (BEFORE R.K. DESHPANDE, J.),Gangadhar Nanaji Milmlile, *Versus* Western Coalfields Ltd., Nagpur ,F.A. Nos. 45, 47, 48 and 56 to 59 of 2005,Decided on May 2, 2016, 2016, SCC OnLine Bom 8197
- xxx (BEFORE B.P. DHARMADHIKARI, R.K. DESHPANDE AND P.N. DESHMUKH, JJ.),State of Maharashtra ,*Versus* Kailash Shiva Rangari ,F.A. No. 251 of 2003,Decided on April 18,2016,2016 SCC OnLine Bom 2236,
- xxxi (BEFORE R.K. DESHPANDE, J.),First Appeal No. 173 of 2002,Dr. Purushottam Dattulal Paldiwal, R/o Paldiwal Hospital, Giripeth, Amravati Road, Nagpur-440 010 *Versus* 1. State of Maharashtra, through Special Land Acquisition Officer, and Sub-Divisional Officer, Khamgaon, Dist. Buldhana, Decided on 21/11/2015, 2015 SCC OnLine Bom 5846
- xxxii (BEFORE VASANTI A. NAIK AND C.V. BHADANG, JJ.),State of Maharashtra and others *Versus* Namdeo s/o Champat Kshirsagar ,F.A. No. 651 of 1994 with Cross Objection No. 2 of 2015,Decided on June 11, 2015, 2015 SCC OnLine Bom 8268
- xxxiii (BEFORE B.P. DHARMADHIKARI AND A.M. BADAR, JJ.),Panjabrao s/o Ganpatrao Borade *Versus* State of Maharashtra and others ,W.P. No. 4274 of 2014,Decided on March 9, 2015, 2015 SCC OnLine Bom 8283
- xxxiv (BEFORE B.P. DHARMADHIKARI AND A.M. BADAR, JJ.),Tukaram *Versus* State of Maharashtra, Through Government Pleader, High Court of Bombay and Others ,Writ Petition No. 4415 of 2014,Decided on December 15, 2014, 2014 SCC OnLine Bom 2140
- xxxv (BEFORE S.C. DHARMADHIKARI AND RAVINDRA V. GHUGE, JJ.),Datta Rao s/o Kerbarao Deshmukh and others ... Petitioners; *Versus* State of Maharashtra and others ... Respondents,W.P. No. 7540 of 2011,Decided on February 24, 2014, 2014 SCC OnLine Bom 263
- xxxvi Bench: A.S. Oka, S.C. Gupte, Bombay High Court, Sushma Murlidhar Ghadge & Another vs The State Of Maharashtra & Others, Writ Petition No. 4121/2013 with connected Petitions , Decided on 13 December, 2013.
- xxxvii (BEFORE R.D. DHANUKA AND S.M. MODAK, JJ.), In the High Court of Bombay Trimbak Joma Thakur (Since Deceased) Through His Lr and Heirs Dashrath Trimbak Thakur and Others *Versus* Principal Secretary, Urban Development Department and Others , W.P. No. 2087 of 2021 with I.A. No. 3555 of 2022, Decided on April 29, 2022), 2022 SCC OnLine Bom 944

xxxviii The Report (1994-1995) on the Land Acquisition Act, 1894 of the Standing Committee (10th Lok Sabha) was presented to Lok Sabha on 15-12-1994 and laid in Rajya Sabha on 13-12-1994

xxxix (BEFORE K.U. CHANDIWAL, J.), 2014 SCC OnLine Bom 114, Bhikubee w/o Anwar Shah ... Appellant; *Versus* State of Maharashtra and another ... Respondents, F.A. No. 2910 of 2013, Decided on January 22, 2014